

The Neuroanatomical Features of Albert Einstein's Brain

I came across this exclusive letter dated 1979 among the correspondence preserved by my father, Dr. Nouri Jaffar, which I now publish for the first time. The letter was written by Dr. H. M. Zimmerman, the neuropathologist who examined Albert Einstein's brain postmortem. A pioneer in the study of nervous system disorders, Dr. Zimmerman also founded the Albert Einstein College of Medicine in New York City. Prior to Einstein's death, Zimmerman had obtained the scientist's explicit consent to study his brain in search of potential neuroanatomical correlates of his extraordinary cognitive abilities.

This correspondence particularly captured my attention due to its significant implications regarding my father's academic aspirations and research interests. The content of the letter clearly indicates it was written in response to correspondence my father had previously sent to Montefiore Hospital in the Bronx borough of New York City, United States. The original communication was subsequently forwarded to Dr. Zimmerman, who assumed responsibility for crafting the institutional response.

The postmortem examination and neuroanatomical analysis of Dr. Albert Einstein's brain were conducted at this medical institution, following his explicit consent to donate his brain for scientific investigation. It appears my father became aware of this procedure, which profoundly stimulated his scientific curiosity. Consequently, he corresponded with the research team to inquire about the autopsy findings, given their relevance to his scholarly focus on human creativity and brain mechanisms. This academic interest was particularly timely, as he was then engaged in developing Iraq's gifted education program.

Of particular note are Dr. Nouri Jaffar's sustained contributions as Iraq's representative (indeed, the sole Arab scholar participating) in international conferences on gifted and talented. His presentations systematically articulated his research on neurocognitive aspects of creativity, establishing him as a pioneering figure in this interdisciplinary domain.

One can only speculate about the potential scholarly contributions that might have emerged from my father's research had he obtained the requested neuroanatomical data pertaining to the brain of Albert Einstein—a figure widely regarded as one of the most extraordinary genius of his generation. This speculative consideration arose while reviewing Dr. Zimmerman's

response to his inquiry. And I leave it to you dear scholars and researchers to think about the potential connections between this piece of information and Dr. Nouri Jaffar's contemporary publications, theoretical frameworks and empirical investigations into cognitive exceptionalism during this period.

Nijood Nouri Jaffar

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September 24, 1979

Dr. Nouri Jaffar
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Dear Dr. Jaffar:

The letter you sent to Montefiore Hospital concerning the post-mortem examination of Professor Albert Einstein was referred to me. I want to respond promptly, but unfortunately I cannot comply with your request for a copy of the report of my findings. This is because permission to examine Professor Einstein's brain was given by his family and his executor with the specific request that I never submit a report for publication. This was done by the family because they felt that Dr. Einstein would want to avoid publicity of all kinds.

I can only therefore tell you that the brain weighed 1350 grams prior to fixation and that both macroscopically and microscopically it was the brain of an adult normal man.

Sincerely yours,

H. M. Zimmerman, M. D.

HMZ:dcf

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